

FAILURE CRITERIA FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS
--GOVERNED BY MATRIX AND INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

Base on the work of Refs. (1) and (2), a failure theory which is governed by matrix and interface failure is presented. It also reveals how the properties of constituents and adhesion of interface may affect the strength. The theoretical predictions of off-axis tensile strengths agree well with the experimental results.

1. A Brief Review of Failure Criteria [3,4]

The research on isotropic materials has indicated that there are two different failure modes, the brittle and plastic failure mode. We have to use different failure criteria to predict them. Even for a same material, it may have different failure mode under different stress states. So the envelope of the strength in the stress space should not be a completely smooth surface given by one equation, instead a combination of several segments of smooth surfaces. This means there are different failure criteria in different area of the stress space.

The failure criteria for isotropic material have been extended to composite materials. They are mainly classified into three kinds: the maximum stress criteria, the maximum strain criteria, and the criteria with "energy form" (which are not really an energy form). The third generally has four basic forms. In plane stress condition, they are

$$(i) \quad a_{11}\sigma_1^2 + a_{22}\sigma_2^2 + a_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + a_{66}\tau_{12}^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

$$(ii) \quad a_1\sigma_1 + a_2\sigma_2 + a_{11}\sigma_1^2 + a_{22}\sigma_2^2 + a_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + a_{66}\tau_{12}^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$(iii) \quad a_1\sigma_1 + a_2\sigma_2 + \sqrt{a_{11}\sigma_1^2 + a_{22}\sigma_2^2 + a_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + a_{66}\tau_{12}^2} = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$(iv) \quad a_i\sigma_i + a_{ij}\sigma_i\sigma_j + a_{ijk}\sigma_i\sigma_j\sigma_k + \dots = 1 \quad (i, j, k = 1, 2, 6) \quad (4)$$

Each of them is supposed available for any composites under arbitrary stress condition.

In fact, composite materials are composed physically, and behave as a structure [5], so their failure processes and failure modes are much complicated and varied in comparison with isotropic materials. It seems impossible using one criterion to predict the strength of all kind of composites under arbitrary loading condition, while even for isotropic materials we can't do so.

Hashim [6] suggested that there were four failure modes and associated

criteria.

Refs [1] and [2] supposed that the failure of composite materials, under complex stress state, is governed by matrix and interface. Using micro-mechanics approach, the stresses of matrix were derived, and then they were substituted into the criteria which the matrixes obey to produce the formulations of failure criteria for composite materials.

2. Failure Criteria Governed by Matrix and Interface

The failure of the specimen under even a small off-axis angle is the failure of matrix or interface between the parallel fibers. In this case, σ_1 is much higher than σ_2 or τ_{12} , so it is reasonable to suppose that the failure, in complex stress state, is governed by matrix and interface.

We suppose that while an unidirectional composite is exerted ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}$) stress state, the stresses of matrix are

$$\sigma_{m1} = \sigma_1 / \alpha \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{m2} = \sigma_2 / \beta = \sigma_2 / \frac{2\beta'}{1+\beta'} \quad (6)$$

$$\tau_{m12} = \tau_{12} \quad (7)$$

where $\alpha = 1 + \left(\frac{E_f}{E_m} - 1 \right) \cdot V_f$ (8)

$$\beta' = \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{E_m}{E_f} \right) \sqrt{\frac{4V_f}{\pi}} \right] \cdot \left[\left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{4V_f}{\pi}} \right) - \frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{E_f}{E_f - E_m} + \left(\frac{E_f}{E_f - E_m} \right) \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{E_f}{E_f - E_m} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{4V_f}{\pi}}} \cdot \operatorname{tg}^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{E_f + (E_f - E_m) \sqrt{\frac{4V_f}{\pi}}}{E_f - (E_f - E_m) \sqrt{\frac{4V_f}{\pi}}}} \right] \quad (9)$$

(from [7]) $\beta = \frac{2\beta'}{1+\beta'}$ (10)

σ_{m1}, σ_{m2} and τ_{m12} are longitudinal, transverse and shear stress of matrix respectively.

For woven composite materials, equations (5) and (6) have to be replaced by

$$\sigma_{mi} = \sigma_i / \xi_i \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (11)$$

where $\xi_i = \alpha_i \cdot \beta_i$ (i = 1, 2) (12)

α_1 and α_2 are taken from equation (8) for warp fiber volume fraction V_{f1} and weft fiber volume fraction V_{f2} respectively, while β_1 and β_2 are taken from equation (9) substituted by V_{f2} and V_{f1} , and then substituting the results into equation (10) respectively. The shear stress of matrix is still expressed as equation (7). If $V_{f2} = 0$, then $V_{f1} = V_f$, equations (11) can be reduced back to equation (5) and (6). That is the case of unidirectional composites.

We can not expected to derive the effects of interface on the failure theoretically. It can only be determined experimentally. We suppose the weakness of the surface is represented by the increasing of the stress in matrix, and use two parameters to represent such an increasing.

$$\sigma_{m2} = \begin{cases} \sigma_2 / \xi_2 \cdot \gamma_2 & (\sigma_2 > 0) \\ \sigma_2 / \xi_2 & (\sigma_2 \leq 0) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$\tau_{m12} = \tau_{12} / \gamma_{12} \quad (14)$$

The parameters γ_2 and γ_{12} can be determined by, for example, transverse tensile test and optimal off-axis tensile test [8] respectively.

Substituting the stresses of matrix (equations 11, 13, and 14) into the criteria which matrix obeys, we obtain the criteria of composite materials. For example,

(i) For the matrixes which obey the maximum normal stress criterion, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\xi_1} + \frac{\sigma_2}{\xi_2 \cdot \gamma_2} \right) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\xi_1} - \frac{\sigma_2}{\xi_2 \cdot \gamma_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{C_{12}}{\gamma_{12}} \right)^2} = \sigma_{mB}^+ \quad (15)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \left| \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\xi_1} + \frac{\sigma_2}{\xi_2 \cdot \gamma_2} \right) - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\xi_1} - \frac{\sigma_2}{\xi_2 \cdot \gamma_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{C_{12}}{\gamma_{12}} \right)^2} \right| = \sigma_{mB}^- \quad (16)$$

(ii) For the matrixes which obey the Mohr's criterion, we obtain

a. when $\bar{\sigma}_{m1}, \bar{\sigma}_{m2} \geq 0$, equation (15)

b. when $\bar{\sigma}_{m1}, \bar{\sigma}_{m2} \leq 0$, equation (16)

c. when $\bar{\sigma}_{m1} \geq 0, \bar{\sigma}_{m2} \leq 0$,

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{mB}^+} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{mB}^-} \right) \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\xi_1} + \frac{\sigma_2}{\xi_2 \cdot \gamma_2} \right) + \frac{1}{\sigma_{mB}^+ \sigma_{mB}^-} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\xi_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{\xi_2 \cdot \gamma_2} \right)^2 \right] - \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{mB}^+} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{mB}^-} \right) \frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{\xi_1 \xi_2 \gamma_2} + \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{mB}^+} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{mB}^-} \right) \left(\frac{C_{12}}{\gamma_{12}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (17)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{m1}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{m2}$ indicate the maximum and minimum normal stress in matrix. σ_{mB}^+ and σ_{mB}^- indicate tensile and compressive strength of matrix respectively.

(iii) For the matrixes which obey Mises' criterion, we obtained

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\xi_1 \sigma_{mp}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{\xi_2 \gamma_2 \sigma_{mp}} \right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{\xi_1 \xi_2 \gamma_2 \sigma_{mp}^2} + \frac{3 C_{12}^2}{\gamma_{12}^2 \sigma_{mp}^2} = 1 \quad (18)$$

where σ_{mp} is the yielding stress of matrix.

Eqs. (15) or (16), (17) and (18) are surprising same with eqs. (1), (2) and (3) respectively. But failure criteria governed by matrix are restricted to different matrix or even stress state, and their coefficients depend on the properties of constituents and adhesion of interface. So they reveal the effects of these parameters on the strength of composites. These are significant for material and structure design for composite materials.

3. Theoretical Predictions and Experimental Results

The experiments were conducted by off-axis tension tests with different off-axis angles. Five different reinforcements and two kinds of epoxies were chosen to compose seven kind of laminae with different combination of constituents. Four of them were (1:1), (4:1), (7:1) glass fabric and uni-directional carbon fiber reinforced 618 epoxy. The properties of the constituents were

$$\sigma_{mB} = 712 \text{ kg/cm}^2, \quad C_{mB} = 576 \text{ kg/cm}^2, \quad E_m = 0.35 \times 10^5 \text{ kg/cm}^2$$

$$E_g = 7 \times 10^5 \text{ kg/cm}^2, \quad E_c = 1.6 \times 10^6 \text{ kg/cm}^2.$$

Otherwise, three were (1:1), (4:1) and (11:1) glass fabric reinforced TDE-85 epoxy. The properties of the constituents were

$$\sigma_{mB} = 813 \text{ kg/cm}^2, \quad C_{mB} = 689 \text{ kg/cm}^2, \quad E_m = 0.499 \times 10^5 \text{ kg/cm}^2$$

$$E_g = 7 \times 10^5 \text{ kg/cm}^2.$$

As the torsion failure surface of circular specimen of matrix is inclined surface 45° to the longitudinal direction of specimen, it is reasonable to suppose that both epoxies obey maximum normal stress criterion.

Table 1 The off-axis tensile strengths of specimens with 618 epoxy. (kg/cm²)

		10°		15°		30°		45°		60°		75°		90°
1:1GF/618 V =0.34	exp.	1913	15.4%	1760	8.2%	1340	3.9%	1265	0.4%	1349	3.5%	1760	7.0%	2648
	theor.	2208		1904		1402		1267		1396		1884		2648
4:1GF/618 V =0.31	exp.	2036	18.9%	1819	6.4%	1279	2.5%	1034	0.5%	927	9.4%	832	36.4%	1254
	theor.	2420		1936		1247		1039		1014		1135		1254
7:1GF/618 V =0.34	exp.	2186	30.1%	2027	10.6%	1335	1.7%	1036	0.0%	922	0.7%	867	1.8%	883
	theor.	2845		2241		1358		1037		916		883		883
CF/618 V =0.60	exp.	3200	7.6%											
	theor.	3442												

Table 2 The off-axis tensile strengths of specimens with TDE-85 epoxy. (kg/cm²)

		10°		15°		30°		45°		60°		75°		90°
1:1GF/TDE-85 V =0.30	exp.			1730	1.6%	1511	2.3%	1381	0.1%	1516	2.8%	1703	2.8%	2000
	theor.			1758		1476		1383		1474		1750		2000
4:1GF/TDE-85 V =0.31	exp.			2411	8.0%	1533	1.0%	1258	0.2%	1081	6.3%	1042	9.0%	1150
	theor.			2217		1548		1255		1149		1136		1150
11:1GF/TDE-85 V =0.30	exp.	2390	18.7%	2163	6.8%	1233	5.2%	805	0.6%	577	6.0%	504	2.9%	465
	theor.	2837		2350		1296		810		538		493		465

Table 3 The comparison of the off-axis tensile strength in 0°, 10° and 15° direction

matrix reinforcement	618 epoxy				TDE-85 epoxy		
	(1:1)GF	(4:1)GF	(7:1)GF	CF	(1:1)GF	(4:1)GF	(11:1)GF
0°	2648	3546	3376	10600	2000	3920	5390
10°	1913	2036	2186	3200			2390
15°	1760	1819	2027		1730	2411	2163

Table 4 The maximum normal stresses in the matrix while the specimens failure (kg/cm²)

	10°	15°	30°	45°	60°	75°	90°	Average
1:1GF/618	617	658	685	709	688	665	712	676
4:1GF/618	599	669	730	714	651	522	713	657
7:1GF/618	547	644	700	711	717	699	712	676
CF/618	662							

*Compare with the strength of 618 epoxy (712 kg/cm²)

Table 5 The maximum normal stresses in the matrix while the specimens failure (kg/cm²)

	10°	15°	30°	45°	60°	75°	90°	Average
1:1GF/TDE-85		800	832	812	836	791	813	814
4:1GF/TDE-85		884	805	815	765	746	815	805
11:1GF/TDE-85	685	748	773	808	872	831	813	793

*Compare with the strength of TDE-85 epoxy (813 kg/cm²)

(a) 1:1 GF/618

(b) 4:1 GF/618

(c) 7:1 GF/618

(d) 1:1 GF/TDE-85

(e) 4:1 GF/TDE-85

(f) 11:1 GF/TDE-85

Figure 1. The comparison of theoretical and experimental results.

Off-axis tensile strength of both experimental and theoretical results are listed in tables 1 and 2, and shown in figures 1(a)-(f). Most of the theoretical predictions are agree well with experimental results except 10° off-axis angle which is nearly uniaxial load condition and difficult to perform precisely.

In table 3, it is shown that even though the laminae are quite different, when the off-axis angle increase even only to 10° or 15° , their off-axis tensile strength are approximately equal to each other. This means that in complex stress state the failure is governed by matrix and interface, and fiber strength does not play an important role.

Table 4 and 5 give the maximum normal stress of the matrix while the laminae failure. They are all approximately equal to the strength of the matrix. This again proves that the failure of the matrix, including the effects of interface, governs the failure of the laminae.

4. Conclusion

- (i) The failure of unidirectional or woven fiber composites under complex stress state condition is governed by matrix and interface.
- (ii) The formulation forms of failure criteria of composites depend on the failure characteristics of the matrixes. While coefficients of criteria can be determined by the properties and volume fraction of constituents and adhesion of interface.
- (iii) Even for the same composites, some time different criterion may have to be used under different loading condition.

- (iv) We have to choose different properties of the constituents and adhesion of interface to meet the loading condition of application.

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